

Sensing the Senses: Multimodal Research with Applications in Product Design

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Abstract

When people interact with products, all their sensory modalities are open to receive information. However, not all sensory information necessarily communicates the same message. To understand product experience, designers must know these incoming sensory messages, whether perceived consciously or not. Therefore, we studied (1) the roles individual modalities play in product experiences (2) the correspondences between modalities and (3) the ways people integrate sensory information. In a split-modality experiment, subjects perceived products through a single modality. Vision and touch provided the most detailed product information, followed by audition and, with a distance, olfaction. Also, vision and touch yielded the clearest expectations of what other modalities were likely to perceive. In a study of cross-modal correspondences, subjects matched smells to colors consistently, resulting in characteristic color profiles for different fragrances. These smell-color correspondences seem to be partly mediated by the emotions people experience. In studies of multimodal integration, the relative importance of modalities depended on the product and the type of assessment subjects made. We are now developing a practical design approach that optimizes multimodal unity in a product. First, we choose the experience the product should evoke. Second, consumer research determines the sensory impressions associated with this experience. Third, the designer integrates the selected sensory elements with the technical specifications into a product. Insight into the relative importance of the modalities assists in establishing design priorities.

Keywords: senses, multimodal, experience

Introduction

When people interact with products, all their sensory modalities are open to receive information about the product. Each modality is sensitive to a different type of stimulation and, consequently, not all the incoming sensory information necessarily communicates the same message. Some sensations trigger feelings and emotions, some evoke memories or associations to other objects. Designers who want to understand the user-product interaction have to be aware that product experiences are based on all the incoming sensory messages, whether perceived consciously or not, and on the interpretation of these messages. To help the designer to get insight into the effects of the different types of sensory stimulation on product experience, our studies try to acquire general knowledge on

- the roles the different sensory modalities play in product perception and experience
- the correspondences people perceive between different sensory modalities

- the ways in which information from different sensory modalities is integrated into a product experience.

Our research provides the design researcher with methods that can be used to investigate these issues for any particular product.

Comparing the modalities

To obtain detailed insight in the differences and communalities of the different senses in product experiences, we developed a split-modality approach (Schifferstein and Cleiren 2004). In this approach subjects were presented with real-life products through only one sensory modality: vision, touch, audition, or olfaction. Six simple products were used: a marker, a deodorant, a tennisball, a bag of crisps, a boiled egg, and a can of softdrink. For each product, the same elements of the user-product interaction were presented to a single modality: a video recording (vision), a sound recording (audition), a smell in a glass container (olfaction), or a product presented in a sound-isolated box (touch). Subjects could explore each product at their own pace. They were asked to describe their sensory experience, to identify the product, and to describe the associations and memories linked to the experience.

	Scale type	Vision	Touch	Sound	Smell
Detailed information	7-point	6.2	6.0	4.7	3.0
Difficulty of identification	7-point	1.3	1.7	3.7	4.6
Clarity of memory association to event	4-point	3.2	3.3	2.9	2.8

Table 1, Mean evaluation responses of product experiences (Schifferstein and Cleiren 2004).

Vision and touch turned out to be approximately equally successful in providing detailed information about a product; audition provided less and olfaction the least detailed information. Also, products perceived through vision and touch were easiest to identify and yielded the clearest memories of past events and associations to persons and other products (Table 1).

Subjects also indicated to what extent they had clear expectations of what they were likely to perceive in the other modalities. The source modalities vision and touch provided the clearest expectations for the other modalities (Table 2). Note that the ratings for the four target modalities were more comparable than those for the source modalities: it is not that much easier to predict a product’s appearance than to predict its smell, but it does make a lot of difference where the information comes from. Overall, subjects found it easier to predict what a product would look like or how it would feel than to predict its sound or, even more difficult, its smell. Some of these effects were product-specific. For example, after seeing a deodorant, subjects had a good idea of how it felt and how it sounded, but not of how it smelled. After touching an egg, on the other hand, its appearance and its smell seemed to be fairly clear, but they found it hard to imagine the sound it would make.

Source	Expectation for				
	Vision	Touch	Sound	Smell	Average
Vision	-	6.5	6.1	5.2	6.0
Touch	6.3	-	5.6	4.4	5.4
Sound	5.0	5.0	-	4.0	4.7
Smell	3.8	3.8	2.8	-	3.5
Average	5.0	5.1	4.8	4.5	

Table 2, Mean ratings on a 7-point scale for the clarity of sensory expectations based on the perception in a different modality (source) (Schifferstein and Cleiren 2004).

The interpretation of information that is more ambiguous usually receives less weight in the formation of an overall judgment (Hoch and Ha 1986; Ernst and Banks 2002). Therefore, vision and touch are likely to dominate product perception and experience in real-life situations. Vision is likely to have an even larger impact on product experiences than touch in real-life situations, because visual information is processed more quickly. Also, vision can be used to explore large objects in a minimum of time, whereas this would be impossible for touch. As a consequence, vision has been found to direct, for example, exploration through touch (Heller 1982; Klatzky, Lederman, and Matula 1993).

Cross-modal correspondences

Even though the study discussed above suggests that people find it hard to predict how a product will smell if one has only had a chance to look at it, consistent correspondences do seem to exist between olfaction and vision. We asked 69 women to judge for each of 14 fine fragrances whether 17 different colors fitted with the fragrance's smell (Schifferstein and Tanudjaja 2004). People have difficulty in communicating about smell experiences through words (Engen 1982). Therefore, fragrance companies that want to inform potential consumers of fragrance properties may try to communicate non-verbally through the colors used for the fragrance fluid, the bottle, the packaging, the advertisements, and other promotion materials. Packaging color significantly affects expectations with regard to perfume intensity (dark red more intense than pastel green), sweetness (dark red sweeter than pastel green), and freshness (pastel green fresher than dark red) (Scharf and Volkmer 2000). To determine which colors can be used for a specific fragrance, we determined the degree to which a number of colors fitted with a fragrance.

Figure 1 presents color profiles for 5 fragrances that differed widely in character: DKNY (DKNY), Kouros (Yves Saint Laurent), Indecence Organza (Givenchy), Miss Dior (Christian Dior), and Wish (Chopard). DKNY rated particularly high on saturated orange and yellow, whereas Wish rated high on all red colors. Kouros rated high on saturated blue. In addition, Kouros and Miss Dior obtained relatively high ratings for grey, black, and brown, whereas most other fragrances obtained very low ratings on these colors. Designers can make use of these specific, individually matching colors to design packages that stand out against competitors on the store shelves.

Figure 1, Color profiles for 5 fragrances.

	Average degree-of-fit rating	Number of different color pairs
Saturated colors		
Purple	4.8	2
Red	4.5	1
Orange	4.6	6
Yellow	4.6	15
Green	4.0	12
Blue	3.8	13
Pastel colors		
Purple	5.1	9
Red	5.1	22
Pink	4.9	17
Orange	5.3	12
Yellow	4.9	19
Green	4.6	7
Blue	4.8	2
Neutral colors		
White	3.3	0
Grey	2.8	7
Black	2.2	19
Brown	2.6	10

Table 3, Mean ratings of degree-of-fit and the number of significant differences between odors for each color (Schifferstein and Tanudjaja 2004).

On average, degree-of-fit ratings were highest for pastel colors, somewhat lower for saturated colors, and lowest for the neutral colors (Table 3). Some colors showed many significant differences between odors, whereas others showed almost none. Saturated purple, light purple, saturated red, saturated orange, light blue and light green obtained high degree-of-fit ratings and showed virtually no significant differences between odors. These colors seem to fit with almost any fragrance and can be used in almost any fragrance package or advertisement.

Part of the odor-color correspondence can be explained on the basis of the emotional similarity between an odor and a color. Odors and colors that evoke similar amounts of pleasure tend to be regarded as better fitting (Schifferstein and Tanudjaja 2004): a pleasurable odor seems to be matched to a pleasurable color. This suggests that smell-color

correspondences are partly mediated by the pleasure people experience when they perceive these stimuli.

Integration: How one sensation affects another sensation

Part of the research on multi-sensory integration focuses on the question how perception by one modality affects perception in a different modality. Below, we give several examples with possibilities for application in product design.

Zampini, Guest, and Spence (2003) asked subjects to evaluate the pleasantness and roughness of brushing teeth with an electric toothbrush. They found that tooth brushing was judged to be rougher and less pleasant when the overall sound volume increased and when high-frequency sounds were amplified. Subjects were unable to ignore this auditory information when they made these judgments.

In the food realm, multiple interactions have been described between taste, smell, vision and touch. For example, adding a colorant to an odorous fluid generally increases the perceived intensity of its smell; darker solutions are often judged as smelling more intense than lighter solutions. The appropriateness of the color has little or no effect on the perceived intensity of the odor, but it facilitates odor identification and increases odor liking (Zellner and Whitten 1999; Zellner, Bartoli, and Eckard 1991). Research on odor-texture interactions has shown that increasing the hardness of a gel leads to a decrease in perceived intensity of a flavor, while flavor release from the gel is hardly affected (Weel et al. 2002). Also, essentially tasteless odorants may enhance the perceived intensity of a taste (Frank, van der Klaauw, and Schifferstein 1993).

These examples show that perception in a target modality may be affected by sensations perceived in another modality. The origin of these interactions may differ. The taste-smell interaction probably occurs because people tend to confuse smell and taste sensations, because they cannot correctly localize the stimulus (Rozin 1982). When the odorant and the taste appear to have similar perceptual properties, people may integrate some of the odorant intensity with the intensity of the taste. In other cases, the cognitive associations evoked by sensing something may generate expectations that affect subsequent perception (Schifferstein

2001). Research on individual cases is necessary to unravel the mechanism behind each of these interactions.

Integration: Multiple contributions to one experience

When a person interacts with a product, inputs from the various sensory modalities are integrated to a product experience. How does this integration take place? Studies of the integration process typically try to determine the contribution of each input variable to (an aspect of) product experience.

In one study (Schifferstein 2004), we focused on the relative importance of the modalities during product usage. Eighty subjects reported how important they found the five sensory modalities during usage for 45 different products on a 5-point scale (Table 4). This showed that, for instance, the usage value of a vase was determined mainly by its visual appearance. For a TV, its sound was equivalent in importance to its appearance. For simple tools and utensils such as a hammer the tactual characteristics were of primary importance, followed by appearance. For products associated with cleaning and with personal care, smell generally played an important role in combination with visual and tactile properties. For food products taste was judged to be most important, generally followed by smell and visual appearance. In addition, the tactile properties of foods were also acknowledged to play a relevant role. Going through the list of products, products were found for which the usage experience depended mainly on one modality (vase), but also products for which four or more modalities were important (car, vacuum cleaner, shoes, cookies).

When subjects were asked to rank the five modalities with regard to how often they used them for the evaluation of products in general, vision ranked highest followed by touch > smell > audition > taste. On the other hand, when subjects ranked the modalities with respect to the degree to which they would be missed if they lost them, vision was missed most, followed by audition, touch, taste, and smell (Schifferstein 2004). Hence, audition was given the second place on the ranking list of how much people would miss it, although it was hardly used for evaluating products.

	Vision	Touch	Audition	Smell	Taste
Car	4.3	3.8	4.3	3.5	1.1
Vacuum cleaner	3.5	3.3	4.2	2.7	1.1
TV	4.4	2.3	4.5	1.9	1.1
Couch	4.6	4.4	2.6	2.9	1.1
Vase	4.4	2.9	1.7	2.0	1.1
Hammer	2.7	3.8	2.2	1.3	1.1
Paper	3.6	3.5	2.1	2.8	1.2
Wristwatch	4.6	4.1	3.5	2.0	1.3
Shoes	4.7	4.5	3.0	3.1	1.1
Underwear	4.2	4.5	1.9	3.4	1.4
Deodorant	2.5	3.8	1.7	4.6	1.2
Flowers	4.8	3.1	1.4	4.4	1.6
Cookies	4.1	3.3	1.9	4.3	4.9

Table 4, Mean importance of the five modalities on a 5-point scale during usage of several products (Schifferstein 2004).

Apparently audition plays an important role in people’s lives, which is largely unconnected to product usage. Indeed, audition plays a major role in verbal communication between people, a process that is only partly dependent on industrial products, such as telephones. Taste would also be missed more than expected on the basis of its role in evaluating product usage. This might be the case, because food products are judged to be more important than products in general. Food products are necessary for survival and, in addition, are a source of hedonic pleasure.

Self-reports can only reflect what people are aware of. If some modalities (e.g., smell or touch) affect product experiences without people becoming aware of it, their importance will be underestimated. In addition, people who rate the importance of various modalities for a vacuum cleaner will base their judgments on the vacuum cleaners they know. If a new vacuum cleaner would be introduced on the market that produced a wonderful, nice smell

during vacuuming, there would be more variability on the smell dimension and the importance of the smell modality would probably be rated higher (e.g., Verlegh, Schifferstein, and Wittink 2002). Therefore, we are currently also working on an experimental approach to study sensory dominance.

Multimodal design

The results of the various types of studies discussed above serve as input for the development of a practical design approach that optimizes the multimodally perceived unity of a product. This approach contains several stages. First, the target product is defined in terms of the experience it should evoke with the user. Second, an elaborate consumer survey is conducted to find out which sensory impressions consumers associate with this experience. Third, the designer integrates the different sensory elements together with the technical specifications into a product. Insight into the relative importance of the modalities assists in establishing design priorities at this stage.

Knowledge of the roles of the different senses is important for designers who want to communicate a coherent message to their potential customers. Designers may wonder which messages an existing product communicates through each of the modalities. The contents of some of these messages may conflict, and the designer may want to check for possibilities to change certain product features to improve the coherence of the product experience.

Congruence of sensory messages is desirable from an ergonomic perspective on product design, where coherence helps to clarify what a product is and what it can do. In addition, perceived unity in visual stimuli has been shown to correlate with ratings of aesthetic appeal and liking (Veryzer and Hutchinson 1998; Bell, Holbrook, and Solomon 1991). Therefore, multimodal coherence is likely to be positively related to consumer preference.

An example of a product in which all senses are stimulated to bring about a unitary experience is Alessi's 'Mary Biscuit' designed by Stefano Giovannoni (Figure 2). This biscuit-box seems to enhance the coziness of social visits. Many biscuit boxes are made from metal and feel cold and may contain sharp edges. Through the sense of touch, these boxes communicate hostility rather than friendship. The 'Mary Biscuit', however, is made of plastic, contains only rounded edges, and its shape bears resemblance to a pillow. The box is soft and warm to touch and seems to invite the user to cuddle. In contrast to the metal box,

which usually does not have a smell of its own, the ‘Mary Biscuit’ smells like vanilla when you open it. Because most cookies contain vanilla flavor, the additional smell may enhance the experience of tasting a cookie. In addition, the smell might evoke nostalgic memories of family visits to grandmother and may, thereby, enhance the feeling of sharing an experience with intimate friends or relatives.

Figure 2, Alessi’s ‘Mary Biscuit’ (courtesy designaddict.com)

The ‘Mary Biscuit’ uses all the senses to communicate similar, but also seemingly redundant information. For simple products of well-known categories that are easily identified, designers may not want to design products for which all senses communicate the same message. On the contrary, designers may want to evoke surprise by introducing sensory discrepancies or uncertainties. Examples are a chair made from rope, which makes a person wonder whether it is stable enough to sit on, or a vase that seems to be made from metal but is actually made from plastic, and is thus much lighter than one would expect. The challenge in these cases seems to be to combine familiarity and originality in one design (Hekkert, Snelders, and van Wieringen 2003). Even designers who want to surprise people will generally make sure that the majority of the product information communicates the same message, while only one particular aspect is responsible for the surprise. Our research helps to stimulate designers to explore and apply sensory discrepancies (Ludden, Schifferstein, and Hekkert 2004).

Knowledge of how the different modalities interact can help to improve products. The chance of detecting an important warning signal increases with the number of modalities that communicate the same message (Selcon, Taylor, and McKenna 1995). This gain in performance will occur only if it is likely that all sensory signals originated from the same

source: the signals need to be synchronized in time and they must seem to originate from the same location (Spence and Squire 2003; Spence and Driver 1999).

Awareness of the roles of the different sensory modalities and their interactions will shift the designer's focus from the physical product to the experience a product evokes. Designers can develop a scenario of the sensory events that occur when a person encounters a product (MacDonald 2002), and they can use this scenario as the starting point for the design of a new product. Such an approach is likely to result in interesting and involving product experiences, because such products exploit the full potential of people's connections to the world.

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